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The Translation Strategies Used in Jojo Moyes' *Me Before You*'s Turkish Translation

Jojo Moyes'in *Me Before You* Adlı Romanının Türkçe Çevirisinde Kullanılan Çeviri Stratejileri

ABSTRACT

This paper comprises an introduction, a literature review, a theoretical framework, a methodology, a data analysis, and a conclusion section. In the theoretical framework section, Mona Baker's translation strategy suggestions for professional translators is summarised. The strategies very briefly are: superordinate, neutral word, cultural substitution, loan word, paraphrasing, omission, and illustration. Furthermore, in the methodology section it is asserted that this is a descriptive study which embarks to discover what strategies of translation are used in "Me Before You" by examining how some words and phrases in a number of sample sentences which were randomly chosen from the source text were translated into the target language, in respect to the strategies proposed by Baker. The data analysis part contains the analysis of the translation of randomly chosen difficult to translate words and phrases in relation to translation strategies. Finally, the conclusion reveals that the translator of "Me Before You" made use of several strategies contained in Baker's taxonomy, thereby making her rendering more readable and intelligible.

Keywords: Translation strategies, Mona Baker, Me Before You, superordinate, paraphrasing, neutral word.

ÖZET

Bu makale bir giriş, literatür taraması, teorik çerçeve, metodoloji, veri analizi ve sonuç bölümlerinden oluşmaktadır. Teorik çerçeve bölümünde, Mona Baker'ın profesyonel çevirmenler için çeviri stratejisi önerileri özetlenmiştir. Stratejiler çok kısaca şunlardır: üstün kelime, nötr kelime, kültürel ikame, alıntı kelime, parafrazlama, çıkarma ve örnekleme. Ayrıca, metodoloji bölümünde, "Senden Önce Ben"de hangi çeviri stratejilerinin kullanıldığını, kaynak metinden rastgele seçilen bir dizi örnek cümledeki bazı kelime ve ifadelerin Baker'ın önerdiği stratejiler açısından hedef dile nasıl çevrildiğini inceleyerek keşfetmeye girişen betimsel bir çalışma olduğu ileri sürülmektedir. Veri analizi bölümü, rastgele seçilen çevrilmesi zor kelime ve ifadelerin çevirisinin çeviri stratejileriyle ilişkisinin analizini içermektedir. Son olarak, sonuç bölümünde "Senden Önce Ben" çevirmeninin Baker sınıflandırmasında yer alan çeşitli stratejilerden yararlandığı ve böylece çevirisini daha okunabilir ve anlaşılır hale getirdiği ortaya çıkmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Çeviri stratejileri, Mona Baker, Benden Önce Sen, üst düzey, parafrazlama, nötr kelime.

1. INTRODUCTION

When professional translators embark on rendering a source language text into a target language text they inevitably will encounter problematic lexical items and phrases. Hence Andrew Chesterman argues that "Translators are, after all, people who specialize in solving particular kinds of communication problems" (Chesterman, 2016, p.85). To solve these "communication problems", translators commonly resort to some kind of strategies. Chesterman likens translation strategies to "memes" that "are widely used by translators and recognised to be standard conceptual tools of the trade." (2016, p.85) According to Chesterman, translation strategies are "forms of explicitly textual manipulation. They are directly observable from the translation product itself, in comparison with the source text." (p.86)

Riitta Jääskeläinen asserts that "it is not always totally clear what one is referring to when talking about "translation strategies". (Jääskeläinen, 2009, p.376) The reason for this, she claims, is that sometimes translation strategies are "referred to by different names, such as procedures, methods, or tactics – even "norms". (p.376) Jääskeläinen further argues that there are a number of strategies that deal with solving individual translation problems. These strategies offer a name for the relationship between a source text (ST) item and its target text (TT) equivalent.

Translation strategies, as Laurence Venuti (2001) describes them, are about the task of choosing a foreign text to be rendered and improving a method to translate it. These tasks are devised by a variety of factors that tend to be cultural, economic and political. Venuti divides translation strategies broadly into two categories. On the one hand there are those ones that deliberately “domesticate” while dealing with the foreign text, whereas on the other hand others prefer to “foreignize” with the aim to “preserve linguistic and cultural differences by deviating from prevailing domestic values.” (Venuti, 2001, p.240)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In her article “Looking for a working definition of ‘translation strategies’” Riitta Jääskeläinen (2009) maintains that the subject of “translation strategies” seems to have led to a great deal of confusion in the field of translation studies. In order to help in bringing some clarification to the issue, Jääskeläinen asserts that she has attempted in her paper to offer a summary of a variety of translation strategy applications and to provide suggestions about how to connect the different strategy approaches with each other. The author of this article first embarks on examining “product-related notions of strategy”. Next she elaborates on the process centered approach of translation studies to strategies. Here usually the main concern is about “problem solving strategies”. Finally Jääskeläinen provides a table which is intended to be a “map” where different strategy notions are attempted to be related to each other. (Jääskeläinen, 2009, p.375)

In “Memos of Translation: The Spread of Ideas in Translation Theory” Andrew Chesterman (1997), like Riitta Jääskeläinen, attempts to provide an outline of some major approaches to translation strategies, or in his own words, “a set of strategies that professionals tend to use” (Chesterman 1997). First, Chesterman explores “syntactic strategies”, some of which are “literal translation, loan, transposition, unit shift, phrase structure change, clause structure change, and sentence structure change”. Second, he elaborates on “semantic strategies”, a number of which are “synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy, converses, emphasis change, and paraphrase”. Furthermore, he writes about “pragmatic strategies” which include topics like “cultural filtering, explicitness change, information change, interpersonal change, and illocutionary change.” Finally, Chesterman discusses the influence of issues such as “motivation”, “the significance threshold”, and “compensation” on the strategies employed by translators.

Finally, Obeidat & Mahadi (2019), in their article “The Translation of Arabic Religious-Cultural Collocations in Literary Texts into English: An Application of Domestication and Foreignization Translation Strategies”, attempt to examine to what degree Arabic cultural collocations can be translated adequately into English. The two researchers analysed a number of examples taken from an Arabic novel by Naguib Mahfouz by applying domestication and foreignization strategies in order to discover whether the translated collocations were domesticated or foreignized. They found out that in the two translations into English, the domestication strategy was employed 16 times, and the foreignization strategy was utilised only 4 times. The researchers conclude their study by asserting that they would prefer the foreignization strategy over the domestication strategy as the former helps in preserving the beauty of the source text and transmitting the source text culture to the target language audience, while the latter causes collocations “to lose their function in the target language either as a cohesive device, or as a tool to add beautiful figurative images to the text” (Obeidat and Mahadi 2019).

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In her seminal work “In Other Words: A Course Book on Translation” by Mona Baker (1992), Baker proposes a number of strategies to overcome the problem of non-equivalence at word level between source language and target language lexical items (Baker 2018). Although the writer asserts that she commented only on strategies for tackling non-equivalence challenges at word level, the author of this paper argues that these strategies can also be applied to deal with non-equivalence at above word level such as phrases and word groups. Hence it was aptly implemented in the data analysis section. Having made the above statement, it would be appropriate to suggest that what Aguado-Giménez & Pérez-Paredes (2005) term as “Baker’s Taxonomy” is deemed highly suitable to be utilised as a framework to comment on translation samples in this study. A short summary Baker’s Taxonomy would be as follows:

1. Translation by a more general word (superordinate). A suitable example for this strategy can be found in the way Ayşe Görür rendered the verb “catapulted” where she picked the Turkish word “atmak” meaning “to throw”, which is a more general lexical item than “to catapult” and therefore a superordinate.
2. Translation by a more neutral or less expressive word. Baker explains expressive meaning by the example set of whinge and complain. These two are synonyms but whinge carries an additional expressive connotation to it, which is that it is an annoying kind of complaining.

3. Translation by cultural substitution. In Görür's translation, the lexical set of "charity shop" and "hayır kurumu kermesi" could be stated as an instance for cultural substitution. There are no charity shops in the Turkish context, yet we have "kermes", a community sale event organised for charity.
4. Translation using a loan word occasionally with additional explanation. A fitting example for this technique could be the word "exotic" which has become a loan word in the Turkish language: "egzotik".
5. Translation by paraphrase using a related word: Baker offers the instance of "creamy" to be translated as "a product that resembles cream" (Baker 2018).
6. Translation by paraphrase using unrelated words: Here the suggested example is "affidavit" rendered as "a written communication supported by an oath". (Baker, p.41)
7. Translation by omission: If the translator does not want to distract the reader with extended explanations about an item that is not important enough for the development of the text a translator may simply omit translating one or more lexical items (Baker 2018).
8. Translation by illustration: To illustrate this strategy Baker mentions the hardship of translating "tagged teabag" into Arabic. So, instead of providing a lengthy paraphrase, the translator can add a picture of a tea bag, thus making the text more flowing.

4. METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive study where the researcher selected sentences that contain good examples of hard to translate words and phrases in terms of availability of equivalent lexical items and word groups in the target language. In the selected sentences, the meanings of the relevant words and phrases were looked up in the online Cambridge Dictionary in order to compare and contrast them with Görür's translation of these and to detect which translation strategies she opted to utilise. The aim of this study is to find out which translation strategies the translator of this popular English novel employed and to what extent her choices contributed to the success of her work.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

In this section a randomly chosen selection of sentences will be analysed for their content of translation strategies used by Görür to tackle the problem of finding equivalent items in the target language for words or phrases in the source text. The Source Text and Target Text sentences were obtained from the hard copy of Jojo Moyes' best seller novel "Me Before You" (Moyes, 2012), and from the hard copy of Moyes' Turkish translation of "Me Before You" titled "Senden Önce Ben", translated by Ayşe Görür in 2013 and printed multiple times since then.

Example 1:

ST: The thing about being catapulted into a whole new life – or at least, shoved up so hard against someone else's life that you might as well have your face pressed against their window – is that it forces you to rethink your idea of who you are. (p. 76)

TT: Tamamen yeni bir hayatın içine atılmanın ya da en azından aniden başka birinin hayatına itilmenin – aslında siz de bu hayatın kapısını çalmış olabilirsiniz – en önemli yanı bu deneyimin size kim olduğunuzu yeniden düşündürmesidir. (p. 85)

The translation strategies deployed in this sentence are as follows:

"Catapulted" was translated as "atılmanın". The translation technique employed here is taking a more general and neutral word. Mona Baker calls this the superordinate lexical item (Baker, 2018, p.12). There is no direct equivalent for the verb "catapult" in Turkish. Therefore, it has been rendered into Turkish with the superordinate verb "throw", which is "atmak" in Turkish. This word choice makes the rendition at the same time less expressive, since in terms of expressive meaning, the hyponym "catapult" is more laden than its superordinate "throw". In the context of this story, it stresses the dramatic nature of the way the protagonist is "thrown" into the life of the second most important character in the novel. In the Turkish rendering of the hyponym verb to "catapult" as the superordinate verb to "throw", this expressive connotation has been lost.

The second item of rendering, which is the phrasal verb "shove up against" has been translated into Turkish with a similar technique to the abovementioned case. The translator made use of a superordinate verb in Turkish in order to replace the hyponym "shove up against". She utilised the Turkish verb, "itmek" which can be translated into English as "to push". Clearly, "to push" is a superordinate to "shove up

against”. When faced with the challenge to render “shove up against” into her native tongue, the translator Ayşe Görür came up with the solution to replace it with its superordinate “to push”, for which there is a readily available Turkish counterpart. However, just as we have observed in the instance above, here too this rendering technique leads to loss of expressive meaning, since “shove up against” sounds more emphatic than just “push against” (Turkish Translation of Moyes 2013 p.85).

Another translation strategy employed by Görür can be observed in the way she translated the phrase “you might as well have your face pressed against their window” as “aslında siz de bu hayatın kapısını çalmış olabilirsiniz”. Although there seems to be a mistranslation here, it could be argued that “your face pressed against their window” has been substituted with “bu hayatın kapısını çalmış olabilirsiniz”. So the metaphorical expression of “pressing ones face against somebody’s window” has been omitted and substituted with the Turkish metaphorical phrase “bu hayatın kapısını çalmak”, which means to “knock on the door of this life”. Both expressions could be considered to convey the meaning of “intruding into a person’s life”, therefore Görür’s substitution of one metaphore in the SL with another one from the TL seems appropriate. So this instance could be counted as an example for the cultural substitution strategy.

Example 2:

ST: I was now the conduit to a different world. My mother, in particular, asked me daily questions about Granta House and its domestic habits in the manner of a zoologist forensically examining some strange new creature and its habitat (Moyes 2012 p.76).

TT: Ben artık farklı bir dünyaya açılan yoldum. Özellikle annem her gün çalıştığım ev ve ahalisinin alışkanlıkları hakkında garip sorular soruyor, yeni bir yarattığı ve onun yaşam alanını ciddiyle inceleyen bir zoolog edasına bürünüyordu (Moyes 2013 p.85).

The first instance in this example is the way Görür rendered “conduit” into Turkish. “Yol” means road or pathway in English. The Cambridge Dictionary explains conduit as “a pipe or passage for water or electrical wires to go through”. Therefore, “conduit” could be considered a hyponym of “passage” or “pathway”, which is close to Görür’s choice of rendering. Hence, the strategy used in this case is opting for the superordinate in order to achieve equivalence.

In the next sentence of this example “Granta House” was translated by Görür as “çalıştığım ev”. Here the translator, instead of simply leaving “Granta” as it is, rendered it as “çalıştığım ev” which means “the house that I work in”. So “Granta House” became “çalıştığım ev”. Two items for two items, apparently. Yet, although the back translation that was shown before appears to be too long in English, the Turkish translation contains only two lexical items, making it a suitable choice of translation. The translation technique applied in this case could be called paraphrase using a related word.

In the same sentence, Görür rendered “domestic habits” as “ev ahalisinin alışkanlıkları”. The latter means “habits of the house’s residents”, which is actually what is meant by “domestic habits”. However, there is no way this could be expressed as concisely in the Turkish language. “Domestic” means “ev ile ilgili” in Turkish, so it could have been rendered as “ev ile ilgili alışkanlıklar”. In English this would mean “habits related to the house”. Such a rendering would exclude the inhabitants. Görür correctly interpreted “domestic habits” as the habits of those that live in the house and therefore this could be the strategy of translating by paraphrasing using a related word.

Also in this sentence, the adverb “forensically” was translated as “ciddiyetle”. The former receives two explanations in the Cambridge Dictionary: the first is “using forensic science” and the second is “in great detail”. Facing with such a situation any translator would make a choice by examining the context. The present context clearly indicates that “in great detail” conveys the correct meaning here. Görür rightly chose this meaning and rendered “forensically” as “ciddiyetle” which could be backtranslated as “scrutinously”. The strategy used here seems to be again employing the superordinate to translate a lexical item which has no ready equivalent in the target language.

Example 3:

ST: “This didn’t translate to much - ...” (Moyes 2012 p.77).

TT: “Aslında bu çok şey değiştirmese de ...” (Moyes 2013 p.86).

There is no one to one equivalent phrase for “translate to something” in the Turkish language. Probably for that reason Görür made use of the “paraphrasing using unrelated words” technique in order to solve this

challenge. “Aslında çok şey değıştirmese de” could be backtranslated as “it did not change very much”, which is a successful paraphrase of “this didn’t translate to much”.

Example 4:

ST: “I still looked the same, still dressed, according to Treena, like I had had a wrestling match in a charity shop.” (Moyes 2012 p.77).

TT: “Zaten hala aynı gözüküyor, aynı giyiniyordum. Hatta Treen’e göre bir hayır kurumu kermesinde güreş turnuvasına katılıyor gibiydim.” (Moyes 2013 p.86).

Once more, we have here the implementation of the superordinate strategy. There is no equivalent term for “charity shop” in the Turkish language. Hence Görür struggled to find an appropriate superordinate expression that could do the job. In Turkey, there are no charity shops, but we have charity organizations that organize charity sales usually on city pavements. That is why Görür employed “hayır kurumu kermesi”, meaning “charity sale” to replace “charity shop”.

Example 5:

ST: “Will was unreadable.” (Moyes 2012 p.77).

TT: “Will’i anlamak mümkün değildi...” (Moyes 2013 p.86).

“Unreadable” was translated as “anlamak mümkün değildi”, which seems to be a case of translation by paraphrase using unrelated words. There is no lexical equivalent for “unreadable” in Turkish, hence Görür rendered it by a paraphrase meaning “impossible to understand”.

Example 6:

ST: “- she was too genteel even to raise her voice -” (Moyes 2012 p.78).

TT: “... sesini yükseltirken bile çok kibardı, ...” (Moyes 2013 p.87).

The back translation of this sentence would be: “Even as she raised her voice she was quite genteel.” Although we are obviously dealing here with a mistranslation, what is of interest here for this study is the fact that Görür translated “genteel” as “kibar” which means “polite”. This is clearly again a case of choosing a more general expression, a superordinate, as there is no ready counterpart for “genteel” in Turkish.

Example 7:

ST: “She made me feel like a first class eejit, and consequently I became a first class eejit around her.” (Moyes 2012 p.78).

TT: “Bana kendimi birinci sınıf bir aptal gibi hissettirdiği için ben de o etraftayken birinci sınıf bir aptal oldum.” (Moyes 2013 p.87).

The adjective “eejit” was translated by Görür by opting once again for a more general expression in Turkish which is “aptal”. The Cambridge Dictionary offers “idiot” and “stupid” as equivalents for “eejit”. The former are more general adjectives than “eejit” and, of course, the first expressions that come to mind as translations of “aptal”. Therefore this constitutes again a case of translating by using a superordinate.

6. CONCLUSION

The data analysis section of this study reveals that Ayşe Görür, the translator of “Me Before You”, indeed employs translation strategies when endeavouring to find equivalent words and phrases for expressions of a challenging nature in the source text. The theoretical framework of this inquiry being Baker’s taxonomy of translation strategies of professional translators at word level, which in this paper has been broadened to apply at phrase level too, the researcher embarked on trying to find matches between Görür’s translation strategies and those proposed by Baker. The following strategies were discovered among the example sentences chosen to be analysed in the above section.

The translation strategy that was found to be employed the most was the first one among Baker’s taxonomy items: using a more general word, or a superordinate. 7 instances of the superordinate strategy were identified within the chosen example sentences. Next, 4 specimen for the translation by paraphrase strategy were identified, two of which were with, and the other two without using related words. Furthermore, in two instances the “superordinate” and the “more neutral word” strategies were found to be

overlapping. So two examples of “the more neutral word” strategies can be added to this list. Finally, in one case, the cultural substitution strategy was observed.

As a conclusion, it can be argued that the above analysis demonstrates that Mona Baker’s taxonomy of strategies is indeed used by professional translators such as Ayşe Görür. Although there are occasional mistranslations in Görür’s target text, her skillful use of some of Baker’s strategies adds to the readability and intelligibility of her text. Finally, as a suggestion for further research it could be added that this study focused on the translation of a work of fiction. Other studies could deal with non-fictional texts. In addition to that, other researchers could make use of other scholars’ taxonomies of translation strategies such as those proposed by Chesterman and Venuti.

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